

EFFECTIVE USE OF METHODOLOGY IN PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992083>

Burieva Nilufar Gofur kizi

nilufar.buriyeva.87@mail.ru

Teacher at Foreign Languages Department

Karshi Engineering Economics Institute

Abstract.

Currently, in the modern education system, it is assumed that a graduate of a technical university must correspond to the level of an international professional who knows a foreign language both for himself personally and for professional communication. The use of methods in professionally oriented education helps to increase its effectiveness and stimulates the self-development of the personality of students and teachers. The article examines some aspects of the effective use of the methodology in professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language.

Keywords.

communicative methodology, professional development, professional communication, a foreign language

Introduction:

A foreign language is recognized today as an indispensable component of the professional training of a modern specialist of any profile. When teaching a foreign language, new pedagogical technologies, modern and progressive teaching methods are of great importance. An important role is given to the communicative methodology, which includes modern conceptual principles of communicative teaching of foreign languages, the use of computer programs in teaching and monitoring students' knowledge, various teaching aids and, of course, the professional competence of a foreign language teacher. An important role in teaching a foreign language in technical universities is played by the information and learning environment created by means of new information technologies. Researchers refer to the specific properties of the learning environment as its interactive nature based on communications, saturation with educational resources, the ability to modify and change the goals, content, methods and organizational forms of learning [4, 1090].

Main part:

In the process of teaching foreign languages to students of technical universities, the information and learning environment should ensure a close connection between language tasks and the tasks of professional development of future specialists, maintain a high level of motivation, facilitate the transfer of the main volume of activity to independent work, create a cultural and linguistic environment, and provide a communication component of learning.

Teaching foreign languages at a technical university acquires a new meaning in connection with the transition to an open information society, the internationalization of education with the widespread use of information technologies in many areas of human activity. This is largely due to the forms and methods of practical activity used today, which are the result of the introduction of modern computer technology and means of transmitting information into various spheres of human activity. These methods, based on the broad use of the fundamental capabilities of computer technology for processing, storing, transmitting and presenting information, are united in the concept of new information technologies. Studies show that the means of new information technologies are able to create optimal conditions for organizing control and self-control over the course of the educational process, implement effective feedback, diagnose and correct errors, make up for the lack of a natural foreign language environment at all stages of learning, implement various ways of presenting educational material, create a wide range of incentives to involve students in foreign language speech activities [14,252].

The didactic properties and functions of information technologies contribute to the development of students' creativity and self-realization, critical thinking, interactive and student-oriented nature of tasks and exercises aimed at the formation of professionally oriented abilities. In connection with the increasing importance of language proficiency as a means of narrowly professional communication, teachers have been given the task of developing the skills necessary for future specialists to solve problems related to their specialty. According to the standards, such skills include the collection, analysis, processing and systematization of scientific and technical information in the direction of professional activity using modern information technologies; promotion of the introduction of achievements of domestic and foreign science and technology by means of a foreign language [26,138]. The basis for the formation of these skills are various pragmatic texts, as well as texts related to a wide and narrow profile of the specialty. The condition for students to acquire a sufficiently high level of communicative competence in a relatively short period of time, which would allow

them to freely use a foreign language in any type of activity, is the development of social and communicative creativity in their learning process, which is necessary both in everyday life and in professional activities. An indicator of creativity is the ability to solve problems that arise in the process of interpersonal communication, find a way out of a difficult, sometimes conflicting communicative situation, and use various tactics of behavior to achieve a specific goal [10,133]. As a technique for the development of social and communicative creativity of students in foreign language classes, it is advisable, for example, to use business games, the tasks of which are: improving practical (speech) skills and abilities; training in the use of educational material; development of the creative potential of the individual; increased interest in classes, etc. Business games contribute to the formation of a personal point of view on the situation, lead to its rethinking. It is the spirit of competition that encourages creativity, which allows finding original solutions. The key point in business games is the ability to perform various roles.

Another modern method is self-learning. The development of the creative and intellectual potential of students in the process of teaching a foreign language is influenced by such an important aspect as independent work. In the process of this type of educational activity, various tasks are solved simultaneously.²⁹³ Therefore, working with periodicals in the specialty in this foreign language allows students to get acquainted with the latest scientific achievements. Independent reading of a large amount of specialized literature contributes to the transfer of knowledge into skills and abilities in this type of language activity. In addition, the simultaneous mastery of the translation methodology and awareness of one's own capabilities in terms of studying literature in the specialty and access to professional skills through original specialized literature increase the importance of a foreign language in the eyes of students, their interest in its in-depth study.

Conclusion:

Thus, the effectiveness of professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language in a technical university can be achieved on the condition that priority language skills and abilities for students are developed based on the relevant types of educational activities, as well as the search for organizational and methodological solutions that allow maintaining the efficiency of the process with a less intensive classroom load. learning.

²⁹³ Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Tulaboyev Bekzod Zamon Ugli The role of the independent work of students in the educational process // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-of-the-independent-work-of-students-in-the-educational-process>

REFERENCES:

1. Ahmadovna SM. National components in the structure of speech etiquette in english and uzbek languages. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 94-97. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=755324714995079481&hl=en&inst=8697446408056752236&oi=scholar>
2. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Open Access Repository, 8(03), 130-133. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RK8HX>.
3. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2023). FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS WITH THE HELP OF TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(4), 1635-1642. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7868864>.
4. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2023). INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING TECHNICAL TERMINOLOGY IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(5), 1090-1096. <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/1359>.
5. Buxorova MX, Mansurova GM, Eshmurodov UK. FORMATION OF STUDENTS COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. Theoretical & Applied Science. 2021(2):152-4. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=73RuxO4AAAAJ&citation_for_view=73RuxO4AAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC.
6. Erkinovna, Y. F. (2022). Politeness strategies. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 80-82. <http://www.conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/50>.
7. Khalilova O.A. FUNDAMENTALS OF LEXICOLOGY // Экономика и социум. 2021. №3-1 (82). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fundamentals-of-lexicology> (дата обращения: 12.04.2023).
8. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2022). Teaching Pronunciation Skills. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 5, 279-282. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/888>.

9. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna, Obzorov Islom Ruzievich. Prospects of the energy system in Uzbekistan. *Int J Appl Res* 2020;6(5):306-307. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/?year=2020&vol=6&issue=5&part=E&ArticleId=6717>.
10. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). CLT PLAY AN IMPORTANT ROLE TO LEARN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 21, 133-136. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/2571>.
11. Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>.
12. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *ajps* [Internet]. 2022 Nov. 8 [cited 2023 Apr. 24];2(11):11-6. Available from: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ajps/article/view/460>.
13. Khujanovich, E. U. (2023). The Effectiveness of using Mobile Applications in Teaching a Foreign Language. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 288–292. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1150>.
14. Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2023). Basic Principles of Teaching a Communicative Approach in a Foreign Language. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 252–257. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1141>.
15. Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2022). Principles of TECHNOLOGY for Teaching Listening. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(5), 269-274. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/409938-principles-of-technology-for-teaching-li-29ce0406.pdf>.
16. Kholmamatovna, B. L. . . (2021). The Importance of Foreign Language Proficiency for Oil and Gas Industry Specialists. *IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 1(5), 167–170. <http://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/317>.
17. Mirkhaydarovna, J. S., Irkinovna, D. N., Abdimuminovna, C. S., Shamsievna, I. P., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2023). Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(2S), 3518-3528.
18. <http://sifisheressciences.com/journal/index.php/journal/article/view/1589>.

19. Erkinovna, Y. F. (2021). Politeness and culture. International conference on multidisciplinary research and innovative technologies, 2, 82–86. <http://mrit.academiascience.org/index.php/mrit/article/view/96>.
20. Habibovna, U. Z. . (2023). The Main Features of Analyses on “I, Robot” by Isaac Asimov. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS*, 2(4), 206–210. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJLLAL/article/view/1552>.
21. Hikmatovna, A. N., & Kobilova, N. S. (2021). Sociocultural aspects of linguoculture" clothing" in English and Uzbek languages, electronic journal of actual problems of modern science. *education and training*, 18-21. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=3281129292436106770&hl=ru&as_sdt=2005&as_ylo=2023&as_yhi=2023.
22. KOBILOVA, N. Literary Psychology and the Principle of the Epic Image. *JournalNX*, 7(02), 306-309. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/342765-literary-psychology-and-the-principle-of-1cb9cf8a.pdf>.
23. Niyazova Yulduz Tashmuradovna. (2023). GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 912–917. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>.
24. Niyazova Yu. T. Comprehend simple grammatical errors and effective ways of teaching grammar / Yu. T. Niyazova // Міжнародний науковий журнал "Інтернаука" . - 2017. - № 5. - С. 43-44. - Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/mnj_2017_5_12.
25. Niyazova, Y. (2022). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF LISTENING TECHNOLOGY. Scientific Collection «InterConf», (110), 93–98. Retrieved from <https://archive.interconf.center/index.php/conference-proceeding/article/view/455>
26. Ruzieva, N. X., & Yuldasheva, F. E. (2017). The use of mingles in the communicative way of teaching. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (1 (1)), 138- 139. <https://www.internauka.com/uploads/public/14846000251146.pdf>.
27. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // *Достижения науки и образования*. 2017. №4 (17). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>
28. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna, & Azimova Maftuna Shavkatovna. (2021). USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING English. Euro-

Asia Conferences, 14-17. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/519>

29. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna, Nurullayev Bahrom Komiljonovich Information-communication technologies and multimedia in foreign language classes // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №6 (47). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/information-communication-technologies-and-multimedia-in-foreign-language-classes>.

30. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Tulaboyev Bekzod Zamon Ugli The role of the independent work of students in the educational process // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-of-the-independent-work-of-students-in-the-educational-process>.

31. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna. (2021). LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTS. Euro-Asia Conferences, 41-44. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/529>

32. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Teaching speaking for non-linguistic students // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teaching-speaking-for-non-linguistic-students>.

33. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Murodov Bekhruzjon Teaching and learning English through information and communication technologies // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teaching-and-learning-english-through-information-and-communication-technologies>.

34. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna The formation and development of professional-oriented listening in a technical Institute // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №8-3 (49). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-formation-and-development-of-professional-oriented-listening-in-a-technical-institute>.

35. Saidov, X. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОКРАЩЕНИЙ И ИНИЦИАЛИЗМОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 27(27). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8735.

36. Saidov, K. S. (2022). LANGUAGE EVOLUTION AND LANGUAGE ECONOMY. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE " INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION", 1(4), 108-115. Retrieved from <http://academicsresearch.ru/index.php/iscitspe/article/view/1019>.

37. Saidov, K. (2022, August). TELESCOPIC WORDS IN MODERN ENGLISH. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC*

SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 154-162).
https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=16168631530126395931.

38. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 594-600. <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/1055>.

39. Sulaymonbekovna, Q. N., & Raimovna, I. G. (2021). Cognitive dissonance and pragmatic influence. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 902-908. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:aca&volume=11&issue=10&article=136>.

40. Usmonova Z., Quvvatova D. The features of artistic functions in scientific fantasy (using the example of Ray Bradbury and Isaac Asimov's works) //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. <https://saarj.com> Vol. 11, Issue 3, March 2021 Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 7.492

41. Usmonova, Z. H. (2021). The peculiarity of fantastic works (on the example of the works of Ray Bradbury, Isaac Asimov and Stephen King). European Scholar Journal, 2(4), 499-503. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/394826-none-ac04ea4d.pdf>

42. Usmonova Zarina Habibovna. (2022). The Implementing Author's Vivid Speculation of the Technologically Advanced Era in the "I Robot" By Isacc Asimov. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 7, 63-65. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/1019>.

43. Usmonova Z, Quvvatova D. The features of artistic functions in scientific fantasy (using the example of Ray Bradbury and Isaac Asimov's works). ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. <https://saarj.com>. 2021 Mar;11(3). <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=12431019521020205553&hl=en&oi=scholar>.

44. Usmonova, Z. (2021). Artistic functions of scientific terms in work (on the example of Ray Bradbury and Isaac Asimov). *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 5(5). Извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2616.

45. Zarina Habibovna Usmonova. (2021). THE PECULIARITY OF FANTASTIC WORKS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF RAY

BRADBURY, ISAAC ASIMOV AND STEPHEN KING). European Scholar Journal, 2(4), 499-503. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/684>.

46. YULDASHEVA, F. (2023). Этические проблемы в творчестве Алишера навои. центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9271.

47. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 6, 65-70. <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>.

48. Yuldasheva, F. E., & Gulomov, S. (2022, January). POLITENESS LANGUAGE PATTERNS IN REQUEST. In International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online) (Vol. 2, No. 1). <https://ijorces.org/index.php/ojs/article/view/152>.

49. Бадалова, Л. Х. (2016). Проблемно-диалогическое обучение как способ решения учебной задачи. Молодой ученый, (11), 1415-1417. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=26425135>

50. Бадалова, Л. Х. Процесс преподавания психолого-педагогических дисциплин / Л. Х. Бадалова. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2018. – № 11 (197). – С. 130-131. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/197/48690>.

51. Буриева, Н. Г. Approaches to teaching writing in English / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 411-413. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39353/>.

52. Буриева, Н. Г. Using songs and music in teaching English to young learners / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 413-415. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39354>.

53. Кириллова В.В. Обучение иностранному языку студентов-нефилологов в информационно-обучающей среде //Языковые и культурные контакты различных народов: сб. материалов Всерос. науч.-метод. конф. Пенза, 2003.

54. Сайфуллаева Дилафруз Ахмадовна, Содикова Азиза Хайитовна, Солиева Мунаввар Ахмадовна РАЗВИТИЕ НАВЫКОВ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ И ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ РАБОТЫ СТУДЕНТОВ ПО ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫМ ПРЕДМЕТАМ ПО НАПРАВЛЕНИЯМ БАКАЛАВРИАТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Вестник науки и образования. 2020. №19-2 (97). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitie-navykov-samostoyatelnoy-i->

[tvorcheskoy-raboty-studentov-po-obscheobrazovatelnyim-predmetam-po-napravleniyam-bakalavriata-](#)

55. Солиева, М. (2021). ASSESSING THE KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS ON THE MOODLE PLATFORM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2547